

THE ROLE AND ROLE OF THE MEDIA IN THE INFORMATION DISTRIBUTION PROCESS

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Today we live in the information age. Because it has become difficult to imagine every point of our marriage without information. From early morning, we are boxed by the latest news that is happening in the world and in our country, either through social networks or sitting in front of television. After all, information has become an indispensable natural right of people today. And the free use of information without any restrictions is strictly defined in the constitutions of many states, in particular, all democratic ones. And the inextricable right to information and to receive information forms the basis of a free civil society.

In general, information is an integral part of this society. Also, the variety of information flow is assessed as a guiding, shaping force for the psyche and consciousness-thinking of the general public. And the role of direct information technologies in the exchange of information and its appeal to the public is immeasurable. After all, these technologies serve as a guarantor of the accurate and correct reach of information. Today, as an information delivery resource, we understand the media (media in the next places). So what is the media itself? How is it defined in our legislation? Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the media" of January 15, 2007

Article 4 describes the media as follows: "in the manner in which the periodic distribution of mass information has a permanent name and is published or broadcast in print (newspapers, magazines, newsletters, bulletins, etc.) and (or) electronically (tele -, radio -, video -, Newsreel programs, internet websites in the world Information Network) at least once every six months, in the manner in which it is¹. This means that all these resources serve as the main figurants in the supply of information to us and in the exchange of information.

We will witness how the media developed if we feed on the early periods of independence. After all, from the first years of independence, special attention

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг "Оммавий ахборот воситалари тўғрисида" 15.01.2007 йил ЎРҚ-78-сон Қонуни.
Электрон манба: <https://lex.uz/docs/1106870>

began to be paid to the comprehensive development of the media in our country. And for this it was necessary to establish a solid organizational and legal basis. There was a need to improve the quality, skill and responsiveness of our national press, turning it into the achievements of the media of developed countries and such a high level of independent organization. And in order to achieve such a high level, further improvement of legislation in this area arose as a need. It was necessary to properly analyze the internal, foreign policy implemented in our country, as well as the changes taking place inside and outside the country, to provide additional conditions for more active coverage, taking into account the variety of processes.

It should be said that during the independence period, the media in our country acquired a special meaning and essence and reached a new stage of development. At the state level, special attention was paid to reforms in this regard. Systematically, work was carried out, and today the media have become an integral part of the development of our society. It is known to all of us that the role of this system in the process of building a legal democratic state, a strong civil society, further improvisation of reforms, strengthening democratic values in the minds and minds of our citizens is important.

The reforms carried out in this area in our country served as an impetus for the comprehensive development of the media. As a result of this, a solid organizational and legal basis has been established, and this process continues.

In our country there are all opportunities for this. After all, since the first years of independence in our republic, gradual reforms have been carried out to radically update the information sphere, ensure freedom of speech and information, support and development of the media.

Continuing with our thought, let's see how freedom of information takes place in our Constitution. In particular, Article 29 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: "everyone has the right to freedom of thought, speech and faith. Everyone has the right to search, receive and disseminate the information he wants"².

In our General Directory, a separate chapter is allocated to the media. In particular, chapter XV of our Constitution is called "media". In particular, its Article 67 States: "the media are free and work according to the law. They are responsible for the accuracy of information in the prescribed manner.

²Узбекистон Республикасининг Конституцияси. // Электрон манба: <https://lex.uz/docs/20596>

Censorship is not allowed"³. All this is extremely important for the freedom of the information sphere.

The freedom of the information sphere and the inadmissibility of censorship in the Constitution, which is considered our main body, the strengthening of norms that determine the unhindered search, receipt and dissemination of information by everyone, as well as the creation of an excellent legislative base, opened the door to wide opportunities for radical changes in the media and for employees of On the basis of our General Committee, several laws have been adopted in our country in order to strengthen the legal framework for the effective establishment of media activities. More than twenty media sectors adopted by our state, openness of the activities of state bodies, freedom of information, journalism and about a dozen other laws, a number of legislative acts also serve the development of more than a thousand currently existing media in our country. As a result of this, so to speak, a kind of national media market is being formed in our country.

Similar legislation and legislative acts adopted above serve to satisfy the needs of our society, citizens for information, to use their information space. After all, the need for information is an integral human right.

The media are at the forefront of today's global information exchange space. Because, the exchange of information is carried out directly by them. Let's see what the media have been studied by scientists from the point of view of law. Acquaintance and research of their thoughts occupies an important place in our research work.

Prokhorov A. Yu. commented on the media as follows. The media today are an indispensable companion of man, they are increasingly penetrating into all aspects of our life. Therefore, often the media are considered both as an indicator of democracy in society and as a fourth branch of power, as a special subject of law, and as a means of political struggle. There are really many definitions about the media. This is explained by the extreme complexity of producing a general understanding of this phenomenon⁴.

Indeed, today it is no exaggeration to say that the information space has managed to become an integral companion of Man and has time to penetrate deeper and deeper into all spheres of our being, life, society. That is why the media we can, without hesitation, today be called the main element in the

³ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Конституцияси. // Электрон манба: <https://lex.uz/docs/20596>

⁴ Прохоров А. Ю. Политико-правовые технологии ограничения свободы слов в современных средствах массовой информации (на примере сети Интернет): Дисс. ... канд. юрид. наук: 23.00.02. - Ростов-на-Дону, 2007.

organization of the conduct of interaction between citizens - society - the state - the driving force.

Continuing the opinions of researchers, Timerbaev T. Looking at an's opinion. Freedom of speech, freedom of the press and freedom of the media are interrelated and mutually dependent components of information acquisition. The real purpose of the media is that it is their dissemination of reliable information. And the dissemination of reliable information can be carried out only in the conditions of full free and independent functioning of the media. This is facilitated by several components, namely: freedom of the press, the equal availability of official and independent sources of information, the Prohibition of censorship, the ability of the media to participate both in price and in other economic or territorial, departmental barriers⁵.

At this point, it is worth noting that today's media is a kind of "view" of culture. We continue to express our opinion with the views of scientists about this.

Lotman Yu. According to M Media it is " a complex organized communicative mechanism that stores information, constantly developing the most compact methods of this. Receives a new one, encrypts messages and decrypts them, translating them from one character system to another." The latest communication technologies make it possible to transfer large amounts of data to unlimited territories, which makes such functions of culture as sanction and permissiveness especially clear and impressive⁶.

In fact, the media today has become a global information system, occupying huge communicative spaces of everyday life and directly implementing the influence of a particular people or Elat on the formation of culture through information transmission.

Many scientists, thinkers, figures have even guessed centuries ago the relationship between the pose of the media and the reliability, effectiveness and completeness of the information they provide. In particular, on the importance of protecting freedom of the press and the Prohibition of censorship, on June 24, 1821, The French diplomat Charles Talleyran delivered a speech in the Chamber of Peres (Upper House of the French parliament), which concluded his speech as follows: "the people have more intelligence than Voltaire himself"⁷.

⁵ *Тимербаев Т.А.* Конституционное право граждан Российской Федерации на доступ к информации: Региональный аспект: Дисс. ... канд. юрид. наук.: 12.00.02. -Уфа, 2006.

⁶ *Лотман Ю. М., Семиосфера.* Культура и взрыв Внутри мыслящих миров С.-Петербург: "Искусство—СПБ", 2000. с. 395.

⁷ *Тимербаев Т.А.* Конституционное право граждан Российской Федерации на доступ к информации: Региональный аспект: Дисс. ... канд. юрид. наук.: 12.00.02. -Уфа, 2006.

Continuing the above points, it should be said that in developed democracies, the relationship between the media and power is built directly on the basis of laws. Relations based on these laws, on the one hand, guarantee the free functioning of the media, and on the other hand, the freedom of speech and thought of citizens in the information sphere, pluralism of opinions in society and the right to control the media by society. During the long period of development in Democratic states, the role, Place and importance of the media in society has changed. In these states, today the media act not only as a means of informing society, but also as a means of controlling the activities of power by society. Therefore, in democratic countries, the authorities cannot directly control the media and use them for their own purposes.

Based on the above, it should be noted that we understand and feel well the importance of the media as we live in today's advanced information age. The influence of the media on the daily lifestyles of the state, society and individuals is clearly manifested by the rapidly changing period today.

